

Exocrine Pancreatic Function modulates Plasma Metabolites through changes in Gut Microbiota Composition

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Supplementary Figure 1. Gut microbiota composition. Stacked bar plot displays the average gut microbiota composition of all SHIP-2 (n=1,319) and SHIP-TREND (n=907) participants.